

UNIVERZA V LJUBLJANI
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**From Learners to Leaders:
THE ART OF PEER TEACHING**

Lesson Plan Example

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Introduction

Welcome to the Mini Teaching Pack, designed to support teachers integrate peer teaching and ICT into their PE lessons. This pack provides a structured and flexible framework to encourage student engagement, collaboration and self-reflection whilst enhancing the development of technical skills.

This package is based on a student-centered pedagogy and is consistent with contemporary educational goals that emphasize meaningful learning and the development of social and emotional skills. It encourages students to take an active role in their learning by using feedback from their peers and video recordings to assess and improve their performance. Through this approach, students develop critical thinking, communication and assessment skills that are useful both inside and outside the classroom.

The proposed teaching pack is organized into five to six lessons and includes:

1. Introduction to the skill with video analysis and goal setting.
2. Skill refinement through practice, peer feedback and self-assessment with or without the aid of ICT.
3. Consolidation of what has been learned through targeted exercises.
4. Evaluation and reflection on progress.

We present two examples, one focusing on athletics and the second on dance. However, the methods can be adapted to other sports.

This innovative approach not only motivates students, but also provides teachers with practical tools to encourage independent learning and improve the quality of teaching. Whether you are an experienced teacher or new to using ICT in PE, this pack will provide you with guidance and ideas to improve your teaching practice.

Take the opportunity to inspire your students and bring a new perspective to your teaching. Enjoy the journey!

Lesson Plan Examples

Lesson Plan 1: Athletics – Long Jump with Run-Up

Teacher: Petra Rankel

School: OŠ Kolezija

Grade: 7

Thematic Unit: Athletics – Long Jump with Run-Up

Number of Lessons: 5

Lesson Objectives

Students will:

- develop leg muscle strength, speed, and whole-body coordination.
- perfect the 6-step run-up technique and improve their long jump performance.
- understand the importance of proper take-off and momentum (converting horizontal speed to the correct vertical to horizontal ratio).
- learn to track their athletic performance and set personal improvement goals.
- develop perseverance in achieving their goals and appreciate the effort they make as they progress.
- find out why some are more successful than others and respect the diversity and differences in individual motor performance.
- find out which sports/disciplines you can be successful in if you are good at long jump.
- understand the importance of safe preparation of the jumping area.
- improve collaborative learning skills.
- refine self- and peer-assessment skills (motor performance) when choosing corrective actions for their own and others' technical errors.

Expected Outcomes

- Understanding which leg is the take-off leg and which is the follow-through leg.
- Correct measurement of a 6-step run-up.
- Demonstration of the long jump with a correct 6-step run-up.

- Understanding of athletic concepts and the ability to track personal progress.

Assessment Criteria

Assessment criteria will be determined in conjunction with the students. *I will be successful when:*

Run-up:

1. I know how to measure the 6-step run-up.
2. I run quickly and decisively.
3. I shorten the last two steps.
4. I push off with a push-off leg.
5. I do not make a transfer.

Take-off:

6. I perform a decisive swing with a stopper leg.
7. I help myself with my hands.

Flight:

8. I pull my push-off leg to me.

Landing:

9. I jump into a half squat.
10. I jump forwards or sideways if necessary.

The Lessons' Structure and Learning Activities

Warm-up:

- General warm-up: easy running, running games and dynamic stretching.
- Special warm-up: athletic drills (e.g., skipping and jumping exercises).

Main Part:

Lesson 1: Watch a video of the long jump phases (take-off, flight, landing) and discuss required skills.

Introduction: Watch a video about the 6-step run-up long jump technique. Discussion: *What abilities and skills does an athlete need to have to be successful in the long jump?*

Analyze of the phases of the long jump and assessment of concepts of take-off and stopping leg.

Test to determine push-off and stopping leg.

Demonstration of measuring the run-up.

6-step run-up exercises.

Closure: At the end of the lesson, students evaluate their satisfaction with their measured run-up using the "altimeter".

Lesson 2: Practice the 6-step run-up, focusing on speed, take-off strength, and arm coordination.

Introduction: Review the characteristics of the 6-step run-up and write them down as performance criteria that you will follow.

Make sure you use the correct terminology (stall, push off, flight, jump, landing).

Demonstrate the 6-step long jump.

Establish the performance criteria for push-off, flight and landing together with the students (use the ball circle system). Be careful to set only a few criteria, especially if the students are not used to observing the movements.

Long jump from the raised platform.

Work in groups of two: Give feedback according to the performance criteria. Students use an observation checklist and feedback form. Teacher gives feedback, helps correct mistakes and encourages improvement.

Closure: *How did the pair work together?*

Lesson 3: Work in pairs to provide peer feedback using predefined criteria.

Introduction: Remember how to observe properly and how to give appropriate feedback.

Consolidation of the 6-step long jump.

Work in pairs: Observation and feedback according to the assessment criteria. Students use the observation checklist and feedback form. The teacher helps with error correction.

Closure: *How is your progress? Where do you have problems?*

Lesson 4: Individual work to correct long jump technique using predefined criteria.

Introduction: How to choose the right exercise to correct errors in technique.

Consolidation of the 6-step long jump.

Based on peer feedback from the last lesson, the students choose exercises to correct technique that the teacher has prepared (e.g. rotation work at stations). The students practice the long jump technique individually. Self-assessment using delayed video playback (time-lapse camera and VLC). Students use a checklist for self-assessment of observation. The teacher gives feedback and encourages improvement.

Closure: *What progress have you made? Where do you still have problems?*

Lesson 5: 6-step long jump assessment.

Introduction: The meaning of competition with oneself.

Consolidation of the 6-step long jump.

Carrying out a competition. The teacher evaluates the technique of the 6-step long jump.

Closure: The teacher leads a debate. *Why did you jump so far? Have all students made the same progress? Where will the 6-step long jump be useful?*

Cooling down:

- Stretching exercises led by various students who explain which parts of the body are targeted by a particular stretching exercise.

Evaluation and Reflection:

- Compare the results of each session and discuss individual progress.
- Students identify areas for improvement and evaluate their own performance and that of other participants.

Lesson Plan 2: Dance – Social, Group, and Children's Dances

Teacher: Katarina Bizjak Slanič

School: OŠ Janka Glazerja Ruše

Grade: 7

Thematic Unit: Dance

Number of Lessons: 6

Lesson Objectives

Students will:

- review the knowledge of dance etiquette.
- review the classification of ballroom dances.
- for the English Waltz (EW): repeat the basic square and the right turn and learn the left turn.
- for the Cha Cha Cha (CCC): learn the basic step, the promenade, and the lady's turn.
- understand the importance of rhythm in dance and in other contexts.
- improve coordination, posture, and movement aesthetics.

Student Outcomes

- Selecting the most appropriate dance based on the type of music.
- Dancing to selected music with a partner EW in a closed dance hold and CCC in open dance hold confidently and in rhythm.
- Applying dance etiquette appropriately in a variety of situations.
- Having a positive attitude to differences in dance abilities and developing teamwork and resilience.

Assessment Criteria

Assessment criteria will be determined in conjunction with the students. *I will be successful when:*

1. I know all three pictures of EW/CCC independently and in pairs.
2. I dance with a classmate to the rhythm of the music without making major mistakes.
3. I follow dance etiquette when dancing (equipment and hygiene, behaviour towards the dancer, respectful attitude toward other dancers).

The Lessons Structure and Learning Activities

Warm-up:

- Group dance: "Just Dance", projected on the wall.

Main Part:

Lesson 1
<p>Introduction: Review and practice dance etiquette using a worksheet. <i>Which rules will challenge you the most?</i> Demonstration of EW and CCC. <i>What do you already know?</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ English Waltz: Practice the basic square and turns first individually and then in pairs. Record the performance, analyze the video, and improve your technique. ○ Cha Cha Cha: Learn the basic step. <p>Closure: <i>How would you like to dance at the end of the lessons?</i></p>
Lesson 2
<p>Introduction: Review the classification of ballroom dances and classify EW and CCC using the worksheet. Watch a video of a top performance of EW and CCC. <i>What is the difference between a school performance and a top performance of EW and CCC?</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ English Waltz: Practice the basic square and right turn in pairs. Learn the left turn first individually and then in pairs. Record the performance, analyze the video, and improve the technique. ○ Cha Cha Cha: Repeat the basic step. Learn the promenade and the lady's turn, first individually and then in pairs. <p>Closure: <i>What are the biggest problems with following dance etiquette?</i></p>
Lesson 3
<p>Introduction: Setting the assessment criteria for EW and CCC and dance etiquette.</p>

Dance "Greeting Card" with a projection on the wall. The dance is recorded and evaluated.
Practice EW and CCC in pairs. Students give feedback in pairs (boy to a girl and vice versa) according to the assessment criteria.

Closure: Dance the "Cowboy Polka". *What progress have you made? Where do you have problems?*

Lesson 4

Introduction: Dance "Greeting Card" using a recording.

Practice the complete choreography of EW and CCC in pairs with video analysis via projection on the wall. One pair of students gives feedback to another pair according to the assessment criteria. *How much progress have you made in EW? How is your technique in CCC?*

Closure: Dance "Macarena". *Where and when will we benefit from the dance skills?*

Lesson 5

Practice the complete choreography of EW and CCC in pairs. Assessment by the teacher according to the assessment criteria.

Repeat "Polka", "Blues", and "Dance with a broom" (using a field hockey stick).

Closure: *How satisfied are you with your performance today and how satisfied are you with your preparation for this assessment?*

Lesson 6

Dance party: The student identifies the song and dances a dance that matches the song (EW, CCC, Blues, Cowboy Polka, Ducks, Macarena, Bicycle, Polka and Broom dance, Limbo). Evaluation by the teacher.

Closure: *How do you feel when you dance? What surprised/impressed/disappointed you while dancing?*

Evaluation and Reflection:

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- Compare the results of each session and discuss individual progress.
 - Students identify areas for improvement and evaluate their own performance and that of their peers'.